

Design and Concept of Polyzwitterionic Copolymer Microgel Drug Delivery Systems In Situ Loaded with Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Ibuprofen

Bistra Kostova,^{1,3} Elena Kamenska,² Dilyana Georgieva,^{1,3} Konstantin Balashev,² Dimitar Rachev,¹ and George Georgiev²

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, 2 Dunav Str., Sofia, 1000, Bulgaria.

² Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University, 1 James Bourchier Ave., Sofia, 1164, Bulgaria.

³To whom correspondence should be addressed. (E-mail: bistrakostova@abv.bg; diljana1977@abv.bg)

ABSTRACT. Nowadays, the modern pharmaceutical investigations are directed toward obtaining of new polymer micro- and nano-sized drug delivery carriers. In this respect, the use of hydrogel carriers based on polyzwitterions (PZIs) is an opportunity in the preparation of polymer drug delivery systems with desired characteristics. This paper describes the synthesis and characterization of micro-structured p(VA-coDMAPS) systems with different compositions in situ loaded with Ibuprofen by emulsifier-free emulsion copolymerization (EEC) in water. The mean size of the prepared microparticles was measured by SEM and particles have been visualized by AFM. The inclusion of Ibuprofen in the polyzwitterionic copolymer microgel systems was established by using DSC. In vitro drug release experiments were carried out in order to estimate the ability of the obtained microgels to modify the release of water-insoluble Ibuprofen.

KEY WORDS: drug delivery systems; ibuprofen; microparticles; polymer carriers; polyzwitterions.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the development of modern pharmaceutical science is related to a great extent with the obtaining of new polymer micro- and nano-sized drug delivery carriers. This is completely reasonable, considering their stability in aqueous medium, extended blood circulation and improved targeting characteristics. Particular interest represents the ability to modify the structural organization of the copolymer carriers by changing their hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance in order to achieve specific properties-sensitivity toward different factors (pH, ionic strength, temperature, and enzymes), specific targeting and bioadhesion (1–4). In this aspect, the use of hydrogel carriers based on polyzwitterions (PZIs) containing anionic and cationic groups in the same monomeric unit represents a possibility in the design of drug delivery systems with smart characteristics. PZIs correspond in high extent to the above-mentioned properties as they have and other important properties (non-toxicity, biocompatibility, and ability to immobilize large amounts of drugs including drugs in the form of salts). The choice of exactly this type of hydrogel polymer matrices is determined by their unique characteristics, which are due to their anti-polyelectrolyte properties (5–8). They are a result of specific structural organization, which is characterized by the formation of dipole-dipole clusters (DDC). In the presence of salt solution DDC destroy to selfneutralizing ion pairs, which leads to swelling of the macromolecules to varying degrees depending on the salt concentration, type of ions, the composition and molecular weight of PZIs.

In our previous paper (9,10), were presented the synthesis and characterization of copolymer nano-sized latex particles based on vinyl acetate (VA) and 3-dimethyl (methacryloyloxyethyl) ammonium propane sulfonate (DMAPS) (p(VA-co-DMAPS)) prepared by emulsifier-free emulsion copolymerization (EEC) in water. It was established that the change of the initial monomer feed led to changes in the type and mechanism of EEC, as

well as the shape, the average diameter and the morphology of the copolymer nanoparticles. Using this approach were obtained copolymer matrices with different compositions, structure and properties that release the drug depending on the therapeutic requirements (11).

Our previous studies (12) were directed toward synthesis of p(VA-co-DMAPS) nanoparticles of different compositions by EEC in situ loaded with drugs having different water solubility. As a model water-soluble drug Metoprolol tartrate (MT) was chosen. Results showed high loading efficiency of MT in situ in p(VA-co-DMAPS) particles depending on the copolymer composition. Data obtained from in vitro MT release kinetics from p(VA-co-DMAPS) showed that they could be used as micro-structured drug carriers.

The possibility for in situ inclusion of practically waterinsoluble hydrophobic Ibuprofen (Ibu) in p(VA-co-DMAPS) microparticles with different compositions during the EEC in water also represented interest. The main problems connected with in situ loading of polymer carriers with Ibu are related to its insolubility in water, which leads to unsatisfactory loading efficiency, resulting in decreased therapeutic efficacy (13). This is the reason for applying of different methods and approaches for improving the therapeutic efficacy of Ibu by its inclusion in microparticles (14–18), nanoparticles(19–25), cubic phase nanoparticles (26), and liposomes (27,28).

The aim of this study was to synthesize micro-structured p(VA-co-DMAPS) systems with different compositions in situ loaded with Ibu by EEC in water. The properties, structure and biopharmaceutical characteristics of the obtained p(VA-co-DMAPS) systems were investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Monomers used were vinyl acetate (VA) (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and zwitterionic monomer- 3-dimethyl (methacryloyloxyethyl) ammonium propane sulfonate (DMAPS) (Merck-Schuchardt, Darmstadt, Germany). Initiator of polymerization of VA and DMAPS in water was potassium persulfate (PPS) (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland). Distilled water was used for conducting the copolymerization of VA and DMAPS. The selected model drug substance was Ibuprofen and was supplied by BASF (Germany).

Emulsifier-Free Emulsion Copolymerization of VA and DMAPS In Situ Loaded with Ibuprofen EEC of monomers VA and DMAPS in situ loaded with the model drug Ibu was carried out in distilled water. The chemical structures of VA, DMAPS and Ibu are presented in Fig. 1. The total monomer concentration was 1.5 M. The monomer ratios of VA/DMAPS in mole percent in the initial monomer mixture were as follows: 10/90 (copolymer hydrogel 1 (CH1/Ibu)); 20/80 (copolymer hydrogel 2 (CH2/Ibu)); 30/70 (copolymer hydrogel 3 (CH3/Ibu)) and 50/50 (copolymer hydrogel 4 (CH4/Ibu)). PPS was used as initiator with concentration 1 wt%. The amount of Ibu was 0.200 g. EEC was conducted in thermostat at temperature $64 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, close to $T_m(75^\circ\text{C})$ of Ibu. EEC was heterogeneous and proceeded at the interface between the two phases- lower aqueous phase and upper phase, containing water-insoluble VA and dissolved Ibu. The lower aqueous phase contained the zwitterionic monomer DMAPS and the initiator PPS. Conversion was determined gravimetrically. The synthesized CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were colloidal solutions—aqueous dispersion of particles of copolymer and Ibu. They were purified by dialysis against distilled water. The purified CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were lyophilized. The latter are white powders.

Loading Efficiency of Ibuprofen

The loading efficiency of the copolymers was determined by the following procedure: Ibu was extracted by addition of acetone from lyophilized CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. The resulting mixture of each copolymer composition was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 15 min, and the solid precipitate was collected. The amount of Ibu in the supernatant was analyzed by UV spectroscopy (HewlettPackard 8452 A Diode Array

spectrophotometer (New Jersey, USA)). Three parallel samples were tested and the average results are given. Loading efficiency in percentage (LE %) was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{LE \%} = \frac{\text{total amount of Ibu(g)} - \text{free amount of Ibu(g)}}{\text{total amount of Ibu(g)}} \cdot 100$$

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of the monomers VA and DMAPS and the model drug Ibuprofen

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The morphology of CH₂/Ibu, CH₃/Ibu, and CH₄/Ibu was determined using Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Jeol JSM-5500, Tokyo, Japan). The following samples were tested: a gel structure of the hydrogels after dialysis and the respective solid particles obtained after their lyophilization. Diluted colloidal suspension in distilled water of the gel particles of CH₂/Ibu, CH₃/Ibu, and CH₄/Ibu was placed on a cover glass and dried in air. The solid microparticles obtained after lyophilization of the above-mentioned gel samples were placed on a cover glass. All samples were coated with gold (Sputter Coater Jeol Fine Coater 1200, Tokyo, Japan).

Atomic Force Microscopy

As a support for the CH₄/Ibu sample was used a freshly cleaved mica surface type Grade V-4 Muscovite (Structure Probe Inc./SPI Supplies, West Chester, PA). The squared mica sheet with size 10 mm was glued to the metal pad. The opalescent suspension of solid particles of CH₄/Ibu, before applying it to the mica surface, was placed in an ultrasonic probe sonicator for 10 min until its partial clearing and 100 μL of diluted suspension of CH₄/Ibu was spread on the mica surface. The tested sample was left for 10 min, and then was carefully dried with a mild flow of nitrogen gas.

AFM studies were carried out using NanoScopeV AFM (Bruker Inc.) at air in tapping mode and room temperature. A silicon cantilevers were used (Tap 300Al-G, Budget Sensors, Innovative solutions Ltd, Bulgaria) with reflective aluminum coating with thickness of 30 nm. The characteristics of the cantilevers as indicated by the manufacturer are as follows: spring constant of 1.5 to 15 N/m, resonance frequency of 150 ± 75 kHz and radius of curvature of the tip less than 10 nm. The scanning rate was set at 1 Hz. All images were taken at resolution of 512×512 pixels in JPEG format and further were processed by means of Nanoscope software. Images from three independent locations of the samples were taken for reproducibility purposes.

Temperature Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The thermograms of pure Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu obtained from differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and the temperature-modulated differential scanning calorimetry (TM DSC) were taken using equipment Mettler DSC Q 200 processor model TC11. Each sample with a mass of 8.5 ± 0.5 mg was placed and sealed in an aluminum pan. Two consecutive scans were carried out: heating processes were repeated several times until obtaining reproducible results. Heating process started from 30°C to 180°C at a scanning rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ at amplitude 1°C for a period of 1 min.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies from CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu

The release profiles of Ibu from CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were obtained using a water-shaking bath (IKASHB 20, Germany). Hydrogel systems with equal volumes (containing 200 mg Ibuprofen each) were placed in dialysis membranes (MWCO 3000 D). The test was carried out in 500 mL aqueous medium with pH 7.4 (PBS) at agitation speed of 50 rpm and a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Aliquots (5 mL) of dissolution media were withdrawn at intervals of 60 min in order to determine the amount of released Ibu. After each sampling, 5 mL of pure medium were added. The amount of released Ibu was determined by UV spectroscopy (absorbance at 276 ± 2 nm) using Hewlett-Packard 8452 A Diode Array spectrophotometer (New Jersey, USA). Each in vitro drug release experiment was triplicated. The study duration was 24 h.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Emulsifier-Free Emulsion Copolymerization of VA and DMAPS in Water with In Situ Loaded Ibuprofen and Their Copolymer Hydrogels

New copolymer hydrogels in situ loaded with Ibu—CH1/ Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were synthesized by EEC of VA and DMAPS in water. In our previous studies, it was found that radical copolymerization of VA and DMAPS in water without loading of Ibu was homogeneous at molecular fraction of the zwitterionic monomer DMAPS (M_{DMAPS}) in the initial monomer mixture $50 \leq M_{\text{DMAPS}} \leq 90$. It was expected that in situ inclusion of water-insoluble (but soluble in the monomer VA) Ibu would influence not only the type of copolymerization, but also the parameters characterizing the process and the properties of the gel particles.

Even before the initiation of EEC two phases are formed: upper oil, containing dissolved Ibu in VA and lower aqueous phase consisting of dissolved DMAPS and PPS in water. In our previous work, it was established that formed molecules of p(VA-co-DMAPS) act as an emulsifier during EEC of VA and DMAPS (10). At the initiation of EEC, copolymer micelles are formed in the aqueous medium with a hydrophobic core, containing molecules of VA and Ibu, and a hydrophilic shell of zwitterionic outside groups of DMAPS. This process could be accomplished through the amphiphilic character of p(VA-coDMAPS), possessing hydrophilic DMAPS and hydrophobic VA monomer units. These properties depend on concentration ratio of the two types of monomer units in p(VA-coDMAPS). Since the initiator PPS is water-soluble, EEC begins with the formation of DMAPS monomer units. It proceeds at the interface micelle-aqueous solution with increasing inclusion of VA units from the micelle hydrophobic core. With the increase of the conversion (q) the hydrophilic micelle shell becomes thicker depending on the copolymer composition. This process continues until depletion of the co-monomers and formation of the copolymer with included Ibu composite.

The preparation of this composite is critical for the dissolution and release of the water-insoluble Ibu. Dissolving of Ibu could be explained with the formation of solvate shell around its molecules, which consists of copolymer solvating agent (CSA). This process is possible only when the creating of solvate shell of CSA around Ibu molecules is energetically favored process compared to the initial hydrophobic interaction between the Ibu molecules. The role of amphiphilic solvating agent is carried out by the newly synthesized macromolecules of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. Figure 2 shows the scheme of formation of the CSA solvate shell around Ibu

molecules. For this purpose, it is necessary that CSA possess both hydrophobic fragments indicated by (solid line) and hydrophilic portions indicated by (curved line). The first one realizes substituent hydrophobic contacts with Ibu molecules, as they are Bcast anchor^ on their molecules. The second react with the water molecules and ensure the stability of the released in the water Ibu. This structure Bhydrophobic core-hydrophilic shell^ formed of CSA and Ibu molecules ensures dissolution and release of Ibu.

The efficiency of forming of solvate shell around the Ibu molecules depends on the molar ratio of the hydrophobic VA and hydrophilic zwitterionic DMAPS monomers in the initial monomer mixture. It increases with the decrease of M_{DMAPS} and is most strongly expressed in CH4/Ibu where the ratio VA/DMAPS is 50/50 mol%. It is expected that CH4/Ibu will have the greatest solubilizing effect toward Ibu molecules. This assumption finds its confirmation in the analysis of the release profiles of Ibu obtained from the copolymer hydrogels.

Some of the characteristics of EEC of VA and DMAPS in water and the copolymer gel particles in situ loaded with Ibu are presented in Table I. From the results it is seen that change of M_{DMAPS} from 90 to 50 mol% effects the duration of EEC (27–42 h), reaching high conversions (q), more than 99%.

The data presented in Table I show that the loading efficiency (LE) of Ibu in CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu is high with no statistical difference between the

Fig. 2. Scheme of the formation of the solvate shell of amphiphilic copolymer solvating agent (CSA) around the Ibu molecules; hydrophobic interactions between Ibu molecules are indicated by a (black circle); hydrophobic fragments of CSA are indicated by (solid line); hydrophilic parts of CSA are indicated by (curved line)

different models, which confirms the effectiveness of the preparation method and these results support the proposed hypothesis about the mechanism of dissolution and release of Ibu. After completion of the EEC, aqueous dispersion of gel microparticles with different compositions was obtained. From the represented results in Table I, it is obvious that the solid particles obtained after lyophilization of gel samples of CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu have different average diameters (d). It was found that with increasing of M_{DMAPS} , d decreased from 828 to 463 nm. Compared with the data obtained from our previous study (11), it could be concluded that the in situ inclusion of Ibu in the gel particles led to an increase of d, compared to d of the particles with the same copolymer composition but not loaded with Ibu. This relationship finds its confirmation from the analysis of SEM data and the release profiles of Ibu from CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu.

The samples of the composites of the copolymers in situ loaded with Ibu obtained immediately after EEC are highly viscous, opalescent colloidal dispersions. It could be assumed that the viscosity of the dispersions is due not only to the composite-copolymer-Ibu micelles, but also to the Ibu-free copolymer micelles with hydrophobic cores consisting of VA monomer units and hydrophilic shells of zwitterionic fragments of DMAPS units. The latter could be regarded as semisolid hydrogels (the so-called colloidal matrices).

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The SEM micrographs of the following samples are compared: (i) aqueous dispersions of gel microparticles of CH2/ Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu obtained after dialysis; (ii) and solid microparticles, obtained after lyophilization of the aforementioned aqueous dispersions. These studies were carried out in order to track the influence of the changes of the copolymer hydrogel compositions (change in the ratio between the hydrophobic VA and hydrophilic DMAPS monomer units) in situ loaded with Ibu upon the morphology of the microparticles before and after lyophilization. The importance of the upper motive increases from the fact that Ibu release rate was investigated just from hydrogels in situ loaded with Ibu after dialysis, but not from their solid samples after lyophilization.

Furthermore, the aim is to check the assumption of the existence of copolymer microparticles non-loaded with Ibu, which is important for the release profiles of Ibu from the hydrogel matrices obtained immediately after dialysis, rather than their analogous solid samples after lyophilization.

Figure 3 shows SEM micrographs of gel samples of CH2/ Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu obtained after dialysis. It is seen that the gel microparticles of the three samples are tightly wrapped with polymer film. This enables the study of only their size. This film is registered only after evaporation of the water at room temperature during the process of preparation of the samples for SEM analysis, and under a vacuum during lyophilization of the same hydrogel sample. A logical question arises about the nature of the film coating. The latter is probably formed from copolymer micelles not loaded with the hydrophobic Ibu.

We consider that each composition of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu consists of two type copolymer micelles with different size and properties. The first type copolymer micelles are Ibu loaded and depending on their copolymer composition swell in water to varying degree. The second type copolymer micelles are not loaded with Ibu and are referred to as gel oligomeric molecules, which are water-soluble. We assume that the second type of oligomeric copolymer micelles create film coating depending on the copolymer composition.

Table I. Characteristics of the Emulsifier-Free Emulsion Copolymerization in Water of VA and DMAPS Loaded In Situ with Ibu; Total Monomer Concentration: 1.5 mol/L; Initiator [PPS]: 1 wt%; Solvent: Distilled Water; T = 64 ± 1°C* Due to the Very High Solubility of CH1/Ibu in Aqueous Medium with pH 7.4 (PBS), We Could not Accomplish Effective Modified Ibu Release, Which Eliminated it from the Present Study

Copolymer No.	D M A P S i n t h e monomer feed (M _{DMAPS}) (mol%)	Concentration of Ibu (g)	Loading efficiency (LE) (% ± SD)	Total conversion (q)	EEC duration (h)	SEM average diameter (d) (nm ± SD)
CH1/Ibu	90	0.200	87.5 ± 2.5	99.6	27	463 ± 21.4
CH2/Ibu	80	0.200	88.9 ± 2.3	99.4	29	657 ± 15.3
CH3/Ibu	70	0.200	90.2 ± 1.9	99.5	31	742 ± 18.2
CH4/Ibu	50	0.200	92.9 ± 2.4	99.1	42	828 ± 10

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of gel sample of: a CH2/Ibu, b CH3/Ibu, and c CH4/Ibu obtained after dialysis

By means of SEM, it has been found that coating copolymer film is destroyed also during lyophilization of the gel structures of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. Figure 4a, c and e shows micrographs of solid microparticles of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu, obtained after lyophilization. In Fig. 4b, d and f, it is seen that the surface structure of the ruptured film during lyophilization varies depending on the copolymer composition. It was found that the ruptured film (whatever the form is) presented around the solid microparticles after lyophilization. Confirmation of this fact is that after dispersion of the solid particles in water the film was formed again, under which they again retained their shape and were stable. These SEM images are not represented in this paper.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the morphology of solid microparticles and the film, which ruptures during the process of lyophilization: a, b CH2/ Ibu; c, d CH3/Ibu; e, f CH4/Ibu

Fig. 5. CH4/Ibu particles deposited on mica support. (a) Schematic diagram of the adsorption process of a single CH4/Ibu particle before the contact with mica, and after the adsorption process. AFM images in b 3D format and c 2D format with the section analysis performed across one CH4/Ibu particle shown with the cross lines at the image. The scanned area was $16.8 \times 16.8 \mu\text{m}$ with z-scale 100 nm. The inset in (b) histogram of the number of CH4/Ibu particles with a particular size versus their diameter.

Atomic Force Microscopy

It is well established that the structure and the size of intact liposomes or nanocapsules could be determined by means of AFM imaging in air by preparation of dried samples deposited on mica following the procedure described elsewhere (29,30). This procedure was successfully applied here for imaging of solid CH4/Ibu particles obtained after lyophilization of the hydrogel. At first, the suspension of CH4/Ibu was appropriately diluted and then $100 \mu\text{L}$ was deposited on freshly cleaved mica surface. In order to estimate the size of the CH4/Ibu, we adopted the mechanism of structural reorganization of the deposited CH4/Ibu at the mica surface which is schematically shown in Fig. 5a for a single CH4/Ibu particle (30). Before the adsorption process the CH4/Ibu particle has a spherical shape, but when it contacts the mica substrate it deforms to a spheroid. Therefore, if we approximate the intact CH4/Ibu particle as a sphere with the diameter d before the contact with mica surface then its volume will be: $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3$, but after the completion of the adsorption process the CH4/Ibu particle will be deformed to an ellipsoid like structure which has volume $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi abc$. Then, to calculate the diameter of the intact CH4/Ibu particle, one needs to measure the sizes of the adsorbed CH4/Ibu particle a , b , and c , respectively, and further to calculate d from the apparent equality $d = 2\sqrt[3]{abc}$.

In Fig. 5b, c are presented AFM images in 3D and 2D format respectively, which display, randomly attached to the mica surface well-defined solid particles of CH4/Ibu obtained after lyophilization of the hydrogel. As an example, the performed section analysis across the CH4/Ibu particle at Fig. 5 gave for the average sizes for $X=2a \approx 2.17 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $Y=2b \approx 2.09 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $Z=2c=0.055 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$. From these measures one can determine the approximate diameter of the CH4/Ibu particles, $d \approx \frac{2}{4} \sqrt[3]{\frac{2.17 * 2.09 * 0.055}{2^3}} \approx 0.63 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$. The statistics for the sizes of CH4/Ibu particles is presented in the histogram inserted in Fig. 5b, which presents the number of CH4/Ibu particles with a particular size versus their diameter. This statistics was based on the total number of more than a hundred particles. It gives for the mean diameter the $d \approx 0.74 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$, which value is very close to the size of the particles measured from the SEM images (i.e. Fig. 3c).

Fig.6. Differential scanning calorimetry thermograms. (left graph)

Fig. 7. Waterevaporationpeaksintheintervalbetween40–150°C (curve1) melt- ing of CH2/Ibu; (curve 2) melting of CH3/Ibu; (curve 3) melting of water evaporation peak from CH2/Ibu; (curve 2) water evaporation peak CH4/Ibu; (curve 4) melting of crystalline Ibuprofen from CH3/Ibu; (curve 3) water evaporation peak from CH4/Ibu.

Fig. 8. Release profiles of Ibu from CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu at pH 7.4 and 37°C

Thermal Properties of the Ibuprofen-Loaded Copolymer Hydrogels

Thermograms obtained from the DSC analysis of crystalline Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu are presented in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6 (curve 4), it is clearly seen the endothermic peak of Ibu at 75.7°C, corresponding to the melting point of the crystalline Ibu at heating and melting enthalpy $\Delta H=135.1\text{J/g}$. The absence of melting peak for Ibu in the thermograms of CH2/Ibu (curve 1), CH3/Ibu (curve 2), and CH4/Ibu (curve 3) shows that, in the presence of these copolymer hydrogels no crystallization of Ibu occurs and it loses its crystal properties, and becomes amorphous. This result confirms the assumption made that proceeds hydrophobic interaction between the molecules of Ibu and hydrophobic fragments of VA and DMAPS monomer units in the macromolecules of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. This hypothesis is verified by the comparison of FTIR-spectra of Ibu, copolymers, and composites of copolymers with Ibu (not included in this paper). No differences were observed in the characteristic bands of the copolymers and the copolymer/ Ibu composites partly because of the big concentration ratio copolymer/Ibu, partly because of the difficulty for registering the hydrophobic interaction in FTIR-spectra.

Figure 7 presents the relation between the irreversible heat flow and the temperature of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. In the thermograms of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu there are water evaporation peaks in the range between 40–150°C. In Table II the temperatures of water evaporation and the evaporation enthalpy of water are shown. It is seen that with increasing of M_{DMAPS} (hydrophilic comonomer), the enthalpy of evaporation increases, i.e. the water content increases.

In Vitro Release Studies of Ibuprofen from CH2/Ibu, CH3/ Ibu, and CH4/Ibu

The in vitro release studies of Ibu from CH2/Ibu, CH3/ Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were carried out with the gel structure obtained immediately after dialysis of the samples, because their possible drug formulation could be a gel.

Amphiphilic character of p(VA-co-DMAPS) depends on concentration ratio of hydrophilic DMAPS and hydrophobic VA monomer units. The bigger M_{DMAPS} is, the higher the hydrophilicity. This statement is valid for aqueous solutions with high ionic strength, when the formation of dipole-dipole clusters (DDC) between zwitterionic side groups of DMAPS monomer units is suppressed by shielding of electrostatic interaction between oppositely oriented dipoles (6,7). The effect of the indicated concentration ratio on the release rate of loaded in situ Ibu in the copolymer microgels at pH 7.4 was investigated in the present study.

Table II. Temperatures Corresponding to the Maximum of the Water Evaporation Peak, Temperatures of the Beginning of the Water Evaporation Peak and the Enthalpy of Evaporation of Water

Copolymer No	Temperatures corresponding to the maximum of the water evaporation peak (°C)	Temperatures of the beginning of the water evaporation peak (°C)	Enthalpy of evaporation of water (ΔH) (J/g)
CH2/Ibu	73.2	38.9	203.6
CH3/Ibu	85.1	41.9	165.9
CH4/Ibu	77.3	40.9	137.2

The results from release studies of Ibu from gel matrices of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu are presented in Fig. 8. As seen from the data in Fig. 8, CH2/Ibu, and CH3/Ibu released 52.77 and 69.6% Ibu for 8 h, whereas CH4/Ibu released 100% of the loaded Ibu for the same period. It has been shown that the reduction of M_{DMAPS} from 80 to 50 mol%, leads to an

increase of the Ibu release quantity about 2 times. It appears that by increasing the hydrophobicity of copolymer (mole fraction of hydrophilic DMAPS units in the copolymer decreases) the release rate of Ibu increases. This result did not confirm our assumptions. To explain this discrepancy it is necessary to assess the applicability of the discussed above hypothesis for dissolution and release of Ibu molecules (Fig. 2). As already explained, dissolution and release of Ibu is realized only when copolymer solvate shell is created around Ibu molecules by the solvating agent- amphiphilic copolymer hydrogel with different composition CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu. This newly formed structure Bcoreshell^ around Ibu molecules and solvating agent is actually the dissolved Ibu and ensures Ibu release in the aqueous medium.

It is important to observe how does the copolymer composition of CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu influence the Ibu release rate at pH 7.4. It is clear that with increasing of M_{DMAPS} the relative part of hydrophobic fragments in the copolymer macromolecule is reduced, which decreases the solvating (dissolving) ability of the copolymer toward Ibu. Therefore, the release rate of Ibu decreases with increasing of M_{DMAPS} . It is possible that significant increase of M_{DMAPS} would lead to an increase in the Ibu release rate. It is logical that high reduction of M_{DMAPS} will lead to a decrease in the Ibu release rate. For example, in pure poly (VA) ($M_{\text{DMAPS}} = 0$) Ibu, probably, would be practically insoluble.

The results of the release studies of Ibu from CH2/ Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu show that all developed formulations could be used as Ibu drug delivery systems. It was found that the Ibu release rate depends substantially on the copolymer matrix composition (concentration ratio between the hydrophobic VA units and zwitterionic DMAPS units) and could be modified depending on the therapeutic purpose.

CONCLUSIONS

New copolymer hydrogels in situ loaded with Ibu-CH1/ Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu were synthesized by EEC of VA and DMAPS in water, as M_{DMAPS} is changed in the range $50 \leq M_{\text{DMAPS}} \leq 90$ mol%. The dissolution and release of the water-insoluble Ibu is explained by the formation of solvate shell around Ibu molecules as a result of the hydrophobic interactions between them and solvating agent (CSA)- CH1/Ibu, CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/Ibu, which have amphiphilic properties. The strength of hydrophobic interaction increases with the decrease of M_{DMAPS} and is highly expressed in CH4/Ibu (M_{DMAPS} is 50 mol%). The results from the release studies of Ibu from CH2/Ibu, CH3/Ibu, and CH4/ Ibu show that all obtained compositions could modify the release of water-insoluble Ibu at pH 7.4 depending on the type of the drug formulation and the therapeutic requirements. It is shown that the Ibu modified release rate depends on the copolymer microgel composition (concentration ratio of hydrophobic VA and zwitterionic DMAPS monomer units). The

compositions CH₂/Ibu, CH₃/Ibu prolong in highest degree the Ibu release—up to 24 h, that is why these systems could be proposed as effective carriers in the cases when prolonged therapeutic effect is desired.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are grateful to ERC grant to S.K.S., EMATTER (No. 280078), and the National Science Fond for the financial support (project DDVU-02/43).

REFERENCES

1. Vázquez MJ, Pérez-Marcos B, Gómez-Amoza JL, Anez-Pacheco R, Souto C, Concheiro A. Influence of technological variables on release of drugs from hydrophilic matrices. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 1992;18:1355–75.
2. Chien YW. *Novel drugs delivery systems*. 2nd ed. New York: Marsel Decker; 1992.
3. Chaudhury A, Das S. Recent advancement of chitosanbased nanoparticles for oral controlled delivery of insulin and other therapeutic agents. *AAPS PharmSciTech.* 2001;12(1):10–20.
4. Kumar RN, Kumar MN. Polymeric controlled drug-delivery systems: perspective issues and opportunities. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 2001;27:1–30.
5. Bredas J, Chance R, Silbey R. Head-head interactions in zwitterionic associating polymers. *Macromolecules.* 1988;21:1633–9.
6. Tsonchev S, Troisi A, Schatz G, Patner M. All-atom numerical studies of self-assembly of zwitterionic peptide amphiphiles. *J Phys Chem B.* 2004;108:15278–84.
7. Chen S, Zheng J, Li L, Jiang S. Strong resistance of phosphorylcholine self-assembled monolayers to protein adsorption: insights into nonfouling properties of zwitterionic materials. *J Am Chem Soc.* 2005;127:14473–8.
8. Schulz DN, Peiffer DG, Agarwal PK, Larabee J, Kaladas JJ, Soni L, et al. Phase behavior and solution properties of sulphobetaine polymers. *Polymer.* 1986;27(11):1734–42.
9. Kamenska E, Kostova B, Ivanov I, Rachev D, Georgiev G. Emulsifier-free emulsion copolymerization of vinyl-acetate and 3-(dimethylmethacryloyloxyethyl) ammonium propane sulfonate and swelling behavior of their copolymer matrices. *Macromol React Eng.* 2007;1:553–62.
10. Kamenska E, Kostova B, Ivanov I, Rachev D, Georgiev G. Synthesis and characterization of zwitterionic copolymers as matrices for sustained metoprolol tartrate delivery. *J Biomater Sci.* 2009;20:181–97.
11. Kostova B, Kamenska E, Momekov G, Rachev D, Georgiev G, Balashev K. Synthesis and characterization of novel drug delivery nanoparticles based on polyzwitterionic copolymers. *Eur Polym J.* 2013;49(3):637–45.
12. Kostova B, Kamenska E, Rachev D, Simeonova S, Georgiev G, Balashev K. Polyzwitterionic copolymer nanoparticles loaded in situ with metoprolol tartrate: synthesis, morphology and drug release properties. *J Polym Res.* 2013;20(2):1–8.
13. Bushra R, Aslam N. An overview of clinical pharmacology of ibuprofen. *Oman Med J.* 2010;25(3):155–66.
14. Win PP, Shin-Ya Y, Hong K, Kajjuch T. Formulation and characterization of pH sensitive drug carrier based on phosphorylated chitosan (PCS). *Carbohydr Polym.* 2003;53(3):305–10.
15. Arica B, Calis S, Atilla P, Durlu NT, Cakar N, Kas HS, et al. In vitro and in vivo studies of ibuprofen-loaded biodegradable alginate beads. *J Microencaps.* 2005;22(2):153–65.
16. Perge L, Robitzer M, Guillemot C, Devoisselle JM, Quignard F, Legrand P. New solid lipid microparticles for controlled ibuprofen release: formulation and characterization study. *Int J Pharm.* 2012;442(1–2):59–67.

17. Castelli F, Messina C, Sanpietro MG, Pignatello R, Puglisi G. Eudragit as controlled release system for anti-inflammatory drugs: a comparison between DSC and dialysis experiments. *Thermochim Acta*. 2003;400:227–34.
18. Gryczke A, Schminke S, Maniruzzaman M, Beck J, Douroumis D. Development and evaluation of orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) containing ibuprofen granules prepared by hot melt extrusion. *Colloids Surf B Biointerfaces*. 2011;86(2):275–84.
19. Hornig S, Bunjes H, Heinze T. Preparation and characterization of nanoparticles based on dextran-drug conjugates. *J Colloid Interface Sci*. 2009;338(1):56–62.
20. Thompson CJ, Hansford D, Higgins S, Rostron C, Hutcheon GA, Munday DL. Evaluation of ibuprofen-loaded microspheres prepared from novel copolyesters. *Int J Pharm*. 2007;329:53–61.
21. Hasan AS, Socha M, Lamprecht A, Ghazouami FE, Sapin A, Hoffman M, et al. Effect of the microencapsulation of nanoparticles on the reduction of burst release. *Int J Pharm*. 2007;344:53–61.
22. Hasan AS, Sapin A, Lamprecht A, Emond E, Ghazouami FE, Maincent P. Composite microparticles with in vivo reduction of the burst release effect. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm*. 2009;73:337–44.
23. DeLeon VH, Nguyen TD, Nar M, D'Souza NA, Golden TD. Polymer nanocomposites for improved drug delivery efficiency. *Mater Chem Phys*. 2012;132:409–15.
24. Ye Z, Squillante E. The development and scale-up of biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles loaded with ibuprofen. *Colloids and Surf A Physicochem Eng Asp*. 2013;422:75–80.
25. Pignatello R, Bucolo C, Ferrara P, Maltese A, Puleo A, Puglisi G. Eudragit RS100 nanosuspensions for the ophthalmic controlled delivery of ibuprofen. *Eur J Pharm Sci*. 2002;16:53–61.
26. Dian L, Yang Z, Li F, Wang Z, Pan X, Peng X, et al. Cubic phase nanoparticles for sustained release of ibuprofen: formulation, characterization, and enhanced bioavailability study. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2013;8:845–54.
27. Paavola A, Kilpeläinen I, Yliruusi J, Rosenberg P. Controlled release injectable liposomal gel of ibuprofen for epidural analgesia. *Int J Pharm*. 2000;199(1):85–93.
28. Mohammed AR, Weston N, Coombes AG, Fitzgerald M, Perrie Y. Liposome formulation of poorly water soluble drugs: optimization of drug loading and ESEM analysis of stability. *Int J Pharm*. 2004;285:23–34.
29. Teschke O, de Souza EF. Liposome structure imaging by atomic force microscopy: verification of improved liposome stability during adsorption of multiple aggregated vesicles. *Langmuir*. 2002;18:6513–20.
30. Momekova D, Momekov G, Ivanova J, Pantchev I, Drakalska E, Stoyanov N, et al. In vitro evaluation of sterically stabilized liposomes as a drug delivery platform for cytotoxic metal coordination compounds of salinomycin. *J Drug Del Sci Tech*. 2013;23(3):215–23.